

Deliverable D7.3

Summary report on use cases

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable, D7.3 – Summary Report on Use Cases, presents the progress of WP7, which focuses on the scientific and clinical GDI Use Cases that guide the development of the Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI). WP7 forms a critical bridge between the technological design of the infrastructure (Pillar II) and its policy, governance, and ethical framework (Pillar I), ensuring that GDI remains grounded in real-world scientific and clinical needs.

WP7 covers four main domains: Genome of Europe (Task 7.1), Building on 1+ Million Genomes (1+MG) / Beyond 1 Million Genomes (B1MG) experience (Task 7.2), Infectious Diseases (Task 7.3) and Cancer Research (Task 7.4). A unified four-step approach has been applied across all GDI Use Cases:

1. Prototypical questions defining core scientific objectives
2. Minimal datasets detailing the essential structured information per domain
3. Data collections identifying real and synthetic datasets for testing
4. User journeys and user stories translating needs into platform functionality

This structured approach has established an operational framework for testing federated functionalities across domains. It has been further strengthened by domain-specific developments that expand and refine each GDI Use Case in line with emerging GDI requirements. Key results include:

- Definition of prototypical research questions and minimal datasets, establishing a shared framework for interoperable data across domains.
- Development of structured user journeys and user stories, linking domain-specific requirements to actionable GDI platform functionalities.
- Successful implementation of federated processing pilot, including the first federated genome-wide association study (GWAS) within GDI.
- Use of synthetic and open datasets to validate federated processes, demonstrating technical feasibility and providing a strong basis for future transition to real-world data integration.
- Alignment of the Genome of Europe initiative with the evolving GDI infrastructure, ensuring coherence between research activities and platform design.

WP7 therefore provides a direct link between scientific goals and technological capabilities, shaping GDI into a sustainable, interoperable and user-driven federation.

2. Contribution towards project outcomes

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following project outcomes:

[Select 'Yes' (at least one) if the deliverable contributed to the key result, otherwise select 'No'. For more details of project outcomes, see [here](#)]

	Contributed
<p>Outcome 1</p> <p>Secure federated infrastructure and data governance needed to enable sustainable and secure cross border linkage of genomic data sets in compliance with the relevant and agreed legal, ethical, quality and interoperability requirements and standards based on the progress achieved by the 1+MG initiative.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 2</p> <p>Platform performing distributed analysis of genetic/genomic data and any linked clinical/phenotypic information; it should be based on the principle of federated access to data sources, include a federated/multi party authorisation and authentication system, and enable application of appropriate secure multi-party and/or high-end computing, AI and simulation techniques and resources.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 3</p> <p>Clear description of the roles and responsibilities related to personal data and privacy protection, for humans and computers, applicable during project lifetime and after its finalisation.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 4</p> <p>Business model including an uptake strategy explaining the motivation, patient incentives and conditions for all stakeholders at the different levels (national, European, global) to support the GDI towards its sustainability,</p>	No

GDI project receives funding from the European Union's Digital Europe Programme under grant agreement number 101081813.

<p>including data controllers, patients, citizens, data users, service providers (e.g., IT and biotech companies), healthcare systems and public authorities at large.</p>	
<p>Outcome 5</p> <p>Sustained coordination mechanism for the GDI and for the GoE multi-country project launched in the context of the 1+MG initiative.</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Outcome 6</p> <p>Communication strategy – to be designed and implemented at the European and national levels.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Outcome 7</p> <p>Capacity building measures necessary to ensure the establishment, sustainable operation, and successful uptake of the infrastructure.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Outcome 8</p> <p>Financial support to the relevant stakeholders to enable extension, upgrade, creation and/or physical connection of further data sources beyond the project consortium or to implement the communication strategy and for capacity-building.</p>	<p>No</p>

3. Methods

The collective work of WP7 followed a shared methodology organised into four interconnected phases, ensuring alignment across all GDI Use Cases while allowing domain-specific adaptations. This methodology was implemented through continuous coordination between WP7 partners from all the tasks and external stakeholders when necessary.

Coordination across WP7 was ensured through monthly Pillar III meetings, where all GDI Use Cases exchanged progress, aligned approaches and discussed common challenges related to datasets, interoperability, demonstrator integration and user requirements. In parallel, each task/GDI Use Case organised its own monthly coordination meetings to advance the work. For some GDI Use Cases, these meetings were also coordinated with the corresponding 1+MG Working Groups to ensure alignment with ongoing European initiatives and standards. In particular, the Infectious Diseases Use Case coordinated closely with 1+MG Working Group 11 (WG11), while the Cancer Research Use Case maintained regular interactions with Working Group 9 (WG9). The Genome of Europe activities were similarly carried out in continuous coordination with the broader Genome of Europe project and its associated stakeholders.

The first methodological phase focused on defining **prototypical questions**, developed collaboratively by each GDI Use Case to reflect realistic clinical and research scenarios. These questions were refined and validated through discussions with researchers, clinicians and members of GDI Pillar II technical teams to ensure scientific relevance and technical feasibility.

The second phase consisted of defining **minimal datasets** based on the requirements identified through the prototypical questions. Building on 1+MG and B1MG outcomes, partners identified the minimum genomic, clinical and phenotypic variables needed for each GDI Use Case, aligning them with FAIR principles and GA4GH-compatible standards.

The third phase focused on establishing **data collections** to support testing and demonstrator activities. Each GDI Use Case identified open or synthetic datasets. Where real-world data could not be used due to legal or ethical constraints, synthetic datasets were created to reproduce the structure and characteristics of real genomic and clinical data while avoiding identifiable information. These collections supported interoperability testing and integration into the MS7 demonstrator and Pillar II developments. The methodology on how these datasets were created can be found in deliverable D7.1¹.

In some cases, multiple "sub-use cases" (referred to as use cases in the corresponding task sections of the document) were created to capture different perspectives within the same domain. For these, different types of synthetic data were typically generated.

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11635576>

Finally, **user stories** were developed based on user journeys², to describe how clinicians and researchers would interact with GDI services. These user stories were refined through continuous exchanges between GDI Use Cases (including clinicians and researchers) and validated through demonstrator activities.

The present deliverable aims to capture and document the results from the common methodological framework, together with the additional domain-specific progress carried out within each GDI Use Case to tailor their outputs to GDI needs.

4. Description of work accomplished

4.1. General coordination

GDI WP7 has played a central role in ensuring alignment across GDI Use Cases and coherence with the broader GDI architecture, particularly in relation to Pillars I and II. This coordination was necessary to avoid fragmentation of efforts and to ensure that use-case development directly informs both governance frameworks and technical infrastructure. In this context, WP7 actively supported the harmonisation of minimal datasets through collaboration with Task 8.2, recognising that interoperable data standards are a prerequisite for effective federated analysis. In parallel, WP7 contributed curated datasets and use case requirements to federated analysis demonstrators³ from WP8, enabling the validation of infrastructure components under realistic conditions and ensuring that technical developments for the federated analysis to take place are grounded in concrete scientific and clinical needs.

From all the steps mentioned in the methodology, there is already a previous deliverable or milestone collecting the results:

1. Prototypical Questions⁴
2. Minimal Datasets⁵
3. Data Collections⁶
4. User Stories⁷

The additional domain-specific progress carried out within each GDI Use Case to tailor their outputs to GDI needs are included in the sections below.

4.2. Task 7.1 – Genome of Europe

² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17661188>

³ https://drive.google.com/file/d/1HRoQBUMCXm7fjx5bUykdXbCBs_t-DaEs/view?resourcekey

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8289477>

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10887528>

⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11635576>

⁷ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17661188>

The objective of Task 7.1 is to coordinate the work with Genome of Europe (GoE) GoE wants to integrate national genome initiatives into a coherent European framework and to establish a population-scale reference dataset that can support research and healthcare applications. This integration is essential to overcome the current fragmentation of genomic data across countries and to enable cross-border analyses at scale. Continuous collaboration with the Genome of Europe (GoE) project has therefore been prioritised to ensure alignment in both strategic direction and technical implementation. In particular, efforts have focused on aligning data architecture and governance models so that datasets generated within GoE can be seamlessly integrated into the GDI federation, thereby ensuring interoperability and long-term sustainability.

To operationalise these goals, three exemplar use cases were developed⁸ in GoE, each addressing a key analytical need: (1) variant lookup in population cohorts was designed to demonstrate basic data discovery and data access capabilities across federated nodes; (2) recalibration of polygenic risk scores (PRS) by ancestry was included to highlight the importance of population-specific analyses and to ensure that risk prediction models remain accurate across diverse European populations; finally, (3) ancestry-specific imputation panels are being explored to support the generation of high-quality reference panels, which are critical for downstream genomic analyses.

These use cases were originally defined within the 1+MG Working Group on Population Genomics (WG12: Genome of Europe). Following a later reorganisation, WG12 was reassigned to Pharmacogenomics, while the consortium activities continued under the GoE project. A report describing these use cases and related activities was submitted by WG12/GoE to the European Commission; however, this document is not publicly available.

4.2.1 Next steps

Future work will focus on synchronising GoE sequencing outputs with the GDI Federated Computation task force, ensuring that newly generated data can be efficiently ingested, indexed, and made discoverable within the infrastructure. Additional effort will be required to further refine governance and access models, particularly in relation to cross-border data use. The GoE use cases will also be expanded and matured to support more advanced analytical scenarios. This includes enabling analyses within specific disease groups, rather than relying solely on the pre-aggregated results currently available, as well as conducting statistical association studies directly within the GDI framework. Such capabilities would support a much broader range of complex analyses. Achieving this, however, will require integration with additional data sources, access to federated compute environments, and related infrastructure developments. These advances would further strengthen the role of the GoE use cases in validating and demonstrating the capabilities of the GDI infrastructure.

⁸ <https://framework.onemilliongenomes.eu/population-genomics>

4.3. Task 7.2 – Building on 1+MG / B1MG Experience

Task 7.2 aims to capitalise on the substantial work carried out in previous European genomics initiatives, particularly 1+MG and B1MG, in order to accelerate GDI implementation and avoid duplication of effort. Building on these foundations, a GWAS use case was designed to demonstrate the feasibility of federated, privacy-preserving analysis across distributed datasets⁹. The GWAS use case was subsequently implemented by WP8 (Task 8.1) as a federated demonstrator¹⁰, providing proof of concept for secure distributed analysis.

In parallel, Task 7.2 has contributed to the validation of a Harmonised Minimal Dataset (HMD)¹¹ within Task 8.2, recognising that consistent data models are essential for enabling cross-study comparability and interoperability. In the same collaboration with Task 8.2, the development of data access policies and phenotype mapping strategies were supported, ensuring that both regulatory and semantic aspects of data sharing are addressed in a coordinated manner.

4.3.1. Next steps

The next phase will focus on supporting the development of an allele frequency browser with Pillar II, aimed at improving data discoverability and usability for researchers. In addition, further work will be undertaken to adapt and extend the HMD developed in task 8.2 to better support rare diseases data in collaboration with ERDERA¹². Continued alignment with previous initiatives will also be necessary to ensure consistency and reuse of established standards.

4.4. Task 7.3 – Infectious Diseases

The objective of Task 7.3 is to enable federated data analysis and discovery for infectious disease genomics, with an initial focus on COVID-19 as a high-impact and well-documented use case. A key achievement has been the development of the Minimal Dataset for Infectious Diseases (MDID)¹³, which comprises 135 items organised across eight categories, including submitter, host, pathogen, disease, treatment, environment, biomarker, and linked data. The creation of the MDID was driven by the need to establish a structured and interoperable framework for infectious disease data, enabling consistent data collection and facilitating cross-border analyses.

⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17989132>

¹⁰ https://drive.google.com/file/d/1HRoQBUMCXm7fjx5bUykdXbCBs_t-DaEs/view?resourcekey

¹¹ <https://health-ri.github.io/HarmonisedMinimalDatamodel/>

¹² <https://erdera.org/>

¹³

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1sx6EEFcXHNblfWVrsk0RIllbep-7Yk4O/edit?gid=1121708571#gid=1121708571>

Close collaboration with 1+MG Working Group 11 and Task 8.2 has ensured that the MDID is aligned with broader harmonisation efforts within GDI as the MDID was included in the HMD developed in Task 8.2.

In order to compensate for the lack of easily accessible real-world datasets (especially with raw sequencing data), two COVID-19 use cases were designed including synthetic datasets—covering both research and healthcare scenarios. The use cases include a defined analysis goal, a genomic dataset with relevant patient annotations, and an analysis pipeline suggestion. Synthetic genomes were generated to realistically simulate published observations, while accompanying annotations were designed to reflect population characteristics, health status, treatment information, and relevant risk factors. The synthetic datasets, which were part of the larger synthetic genomics dataset developed for 1+MG, encompassing some 1 million genomes, enabled early testing of federated analysis workflows¹⁴ from Task 8.1 without the legal and ethical constraints associated with sensitive data. Thus, the use of synthetic data sped up the process of testing the data governance and analysis workflows, by omitting lengthy access discussions or contract development. The data is currently hosted at CSC in Finland, but is not yet public, as the funder (the Finnish Ministry of Social Affairs and Health (STM))¹⁵ has so far not authorized their use outside 1+MG. Ultimately the aim is to allow access via the Finnish FEGA node with authorization from a Data Access Committee (DAC).

Use case 1 addressed a research scenario with the goal of identifying common risk variants for severe COVID-19 (which are helpful to understand disease etiology, and which can help pinpoint drug candidates) using genome wide association studies (GWAS), GWAS were performed very early in the COVID-19 pandemic. The first conclusive result was obtained through the analysis of several thousands of samples from mainly two countries (Spain, Italy; plus a few individuals from Norway)¹⁶. Despite this limited sample size (for a complex trait), a major risk locus on chr. 3 was identified. To identify more loci and include as many populations as possible, an international effort (COVID-HGI) was founded and included dozens of studies. Results are currently published in three data releases in Nature. Notably, the first results by COVID-HGI took much longer than the first individual study, mainly due to the lack of data sharing infrastructure. With the idea to enable rapid GWAS with large sample sizes when a future pandemic occurs, this use case replicated the first COVID-HGI results (specifically: 6 loci associated with critical illness) using synthetic data across several GDI nodes. Risk alleles of these 6 loci were introduced into synthetic genomes in accordance with population frequencies across different European populations (e.g., Italy, Germany, Finland). Meta-data were provided in a phenotype spread sheet. Standard GWAS analysis pipelines can be applied.

In use case 2, we addressed potential analysis scenarios, health care personnel may ask, so called “look up” scenarios: Very severe disease outcome upon infection can be due to monogenic causes. While these are rare, they have a much stronger role in individual risk prediction than common variants. In COVID-19, the most compelling evidence for a monogenic cause are pLoF variants in

¹⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10887366>

¹⁵ <https://stm.fi/en>

¹⁶ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32558485/>

TLR7, in male patients¹⁷. Initially, this finding was obtained by exome sequencing of two families with unexpectedly severe COVID-19 which showed up at one hospital in the Netherlands. Patients could also be distributed across different European countries. A possible scenario for our use case was that an individual does not have any demographic risk factors that would make him/her expect a severe course upon infection. However, this patient is referred to a hospital as he/she feels bad, and sequencing info is available. Physicians may then assume a potential monogenic cause and need access to additional data to understand whether it might be a monogenic condition. This would allow for a more precise estimate of the personal risk and potentially also guide treatment. Therefore, it is needed to know whether any of the candidate variants/genes identified in that patient have been observed in other datasets (i.e., in individuals with knowledge on infection status and disease outcome). The clinician takes the pLoF variant information and looks up variants in the other datasets to see whether any of these three variants (or similar variant types in the same gene) been seen in other individual patients across different data sets, and, if so, what was the outcome in context of the demographic info?

The COVID-19 use cases were further processed by GDI Pillar II to demonstrate the technical feasibility of the infrastructure, and contributed to the development of a demonstrator video¹⁸ for use case 2 illustrating key functionalities.

In addition, Task 7.3 contributed to the Infectious Diseases Toolkit¹⁹ (IDTK), supporting resources related to data analysis, quality control, data description, and data sources. This was achieved in workshop-style GDI-internal team efforts during so-called "Contentathons", where either new information was added, or existing information updated. Eventually the documents were uploaded onto the IDTK, and the GDI contributors recognized, e.g.

<https://www.infectious-diseases-toolkit.org/data-analysis/pathogen-characterisation>

4.4.1 Next steps

Future activities will focus on transitioning the COVID-19 use cases into concrete business cases in collaboration with Pillar I, ensuring their relevance for real-world implementation. The MDID will be further refined and published within the IDTK, taking into account ongoing harmonisation discussions with Task 8.2. Additional work will include expanding the dataset collection to cover a broader range of pathogens, contributing to upcoming IDTK content creation activities, and improving data quality and standardisation to support wider adoption.

¹⁷ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32706371/>

¹⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XZAKgOPSWKo>

¹⁹ <https://www.infectious-diseases-toolkit.org/>

4.5. Task 7.4 – Cancer Research

Task 7.4 aims to establish a data-driven federated framework for oncology, addressing the complexity and heterogeneity of cancer data while enabling cross-institutional research and clinical insights. A major achievement has been the development and publication of the Minimal Dataset for Cancer²⁰ (MDC) in *Nature Genetics*, which now serves as the reference metadata model for cancer within GDI. This work was motivated by the need for a standardised and comprehensive data model capable of supporting both clinical and research use cases across different cancer types.

Regular engagement with oncology experts in 1+MG WG9 has identified some prototypical Cancer use cases (BRAF-mutated melanoma, Acute Myeloid Leukemia (AML), Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer (NSCLC), pancreatic cancer) that reflect real clinical needs and challenges. Based on these interactions, several scenarios were developed using synthetic genomic datasets combined with associated clinical data. The use of synthetic data allowed for realistic scenario testing while avoiding regulatory barriers associated with patient data. The datasets and the clinical questions can be found at the following links:

- Melanoma <https://zenodo.org/records/15754092>
- AML <https://zenodo.org/records/15754623>
- NSCLC <https://zenodo.org/records/15754200>
- Pancreatic cancer <https://zenodo.org/records/15754326>

4.5.1. Next steps

Future work will focus on transitioning from synthetic datasets to real-world oncological patient data, once an appropriate legal basis for data sharing has been established. This will involve exploring integration through national GDI nodes, leveraging the Federated EGA framework, and establishing pilot collaborations with hospitals. Rather than limiting efforts to the cancer types used in the proof-of-concept use cases, we aim to support the integration of all available structured oncological datasets. Addressing legal, ethical, and interoperability challenges will be essential, as these remain major barriers to the large-scale use of clinical cancer data within federated research infrastructures.

5. Results

Across the four GDI use cases, WP7 followed a coherent stepwise process that went from identifying research questions²¹ to testing operational federated solutions²² together with WP8. This structured approach produced tangible outcomes that now underpin the overall GDI framework.

²⁰ <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41588-024-01721-x>

²¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8289477>

²² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17989132>

The unified methodology—based on the progression from prototypical questions to minimal datasets, data collections, and user stories—proved effective for aligning scientific requirements with infrastructure design. It offered a consistent blueprint across very different domains such as population genomics, infectious disease and oncology. Each use case demonstrated that the same conceptual workflow could be adapted to specific technical and ethical contexts.

A central result of this process was the definition of minimal datasets for each domain. These provided the structured, interoperable information models required for GDI to manage and exchange data following FAIR principles. The Minimal Dataset for Cancer²³ (MDC) became the reference metadata model for GDI, to help develop the HMD in Task 8.2.. Similarly, the Minimal Dataset for Infectious Diseases (MDID) captured 135 data elements across eight categories, offering the level of standardisation necessary for federated analysis. Together, these outputs form the foundation for the HMD being validated through task 8.2.

Parallel to the data model development, a catalogue of data collections²⁴ was assembled to enable early testing within the federation. These comprise both synthetic and openly available real data, ensuring that all experimental work remains compliant with current privacy regulations. These data collections were instrumental for the MS7 demonstrator in pillar II.

The creation of user stories²⁵ derived from the use cases provided an essential human-centred dimension to the project. By describing in practical terms how a researcher or clinician interacts with the infrastructure—from authentication to analysis—these stories ensured that technical tools developed in Pillar II remain usable and relevant. Scenarios such as variant lookup, polygenic risk score recalibration, ancestry-specific imputation, federated genome-wide association studies, and clinician-to-clinician consultation were detailed and mapped to concrete functionalities in the GDI user portal. A cross-validation of the prototypical questions formulated by the use cases against the GDI user journeys and stories, revealed recommendations to address remaining gaps.

Several demonstrators validated that these concepts can operate in practice. The federated GWAS pilot²⁶, developed collaboratively between Task 7.2 and WP8, proved that large-scale genome-wide analysis can be performed across distributed national nodes without moving sensitive data. A complementary demonstrator for polygenic risk score²⁷ analysis confirmed that statistical recalibration can also be achieved through federation. In the infectious disease domain, a visual demonstrator²⁸ showing the “Allele Lookup in Severe COVID-19 Cases” illustrated real-time variant discovery using GDI’s Allele Frequency Beacon network²⁹.

²³ <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41588-024-01721-x>

²⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11635576>

²⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17661188>

²⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17989132>

²⁷ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10887366>

²⁸ <https://youtu.be/XZAKgOPSWKo?si=YJw1KlO4N-S-C-gR>

²⁹ <https://github.com/EGA-archive/allele-frequency-browser>

6. Discussion

The WP7 experience illustrates how co-design between scientific communities and technical teams can effectively shape a federated European genomic data infrastructure. Rather than being purely a technical exercise, the development of GDI has been strongly driven by real use-case requirements, which has helped ensure that the emerging infrastructure remains aligned with research and clinical needs.

A key outcome is the validation of the federation concept. The GWAS demonstrator developed under Task 7.2 showed that cross-node computation is feasible without requiring data centralisation, confirming one of the core assumptions of the GDI approach. At the same time, the definition of minimal datasets has proven essential for enabling interoperability across domains and will be a critical enabler for future integration with the European Health Data Space (EHDS).

However, the work also confirms that technical solutions alone are not sufficient. Scalable data sharing across Europe depends strongly on legal and governance frameworks, requiring close alignment with Pillar I and future structures such as the EDIC. In addition, the diversity of use cases—from population-scale genomic studies to highly detailed clinical oncology applications—demonstrates that a single uniform approach is not viable. Instead, the system must remain flexible, supporting different data granularities and operational models while preserving interoperability across them.

7. Conclusions & Impact

WP7 has successfully connected research questions, data models and technical implementation within GDI. It has played a central role in ensuring that scientific and clinical needs are effectively translated into requirements for the infrastructure, maintaining alignment between real-world use cases and developments in Pillars I and II. Through the definition and validation of minimal datasets WP7 has contributed to a common framework for interoperable and reusable genomic data across Europe.

The development of exemplar use cases in Genome of Europe, infectious diseases and cancer research has strengthened the foundations for a scalable and user-driven European genomic data infrastructure by linking scientific needs with governance and technical developments.

The use of synthetic data has enabled validation of federated processes. These results provide a strong foundation for future developments involving real-world data. Ongoing efforts are therefore paving the way towards this transition, within which a potential GDI extension will focus on deploying operational services based on real data, delivering tangible impact for researchers, clinicians and patients.

8. Next steps

Building on the progress achieved across all use cases within WP7, the next phase of work will focus on consolidating, scaling, and operationalising the developed components to ensure their effective integration into the broader GDI framework.

A key priority will be the continued harmonisation and adoption of minimal datasets across all domains, in close collaboration with Task 8.2. While significant progress has been made in defining domain-specific datasets—such as the Minimal Dataset for Cancer (MDC) and the Minimal Dataset for Infectious Diseases (MDID)—further alignment is required to ensure semantic interoperability and usability across use cases. In this context, additional efforts will be undertaken jointly with Task 8.2 to further improve the MDID by incorporating rare disease perspectives and data requirements, leveraging inputs from the ERDERA³⁰ project. This collaboration is expected to strengthen cross-domain interoperability and ensure that the MDID is robust enough to support a broader range of clinical and research applications.

In parallel, efforts will focus on strengthening the integration between WP7 use cases and GDI infrastructure. This includes supporting the final development of discoverability tools such as the allele frequency browser and the federated data analysis tools being developed in WP8. The idea is that additional federated demonstrators will be developed to validate new functionalities, with particular emphasis on cross-border operability and federated learning.

Another major area of work will involve transitioning from synthetic to real-world data. While synthetic datasets have been essential for initial testing and validation, enabling access to real data remains critical for demonstrating the full value of the GDI infrastructure. This will require close collaboration with Pillar I to address legal, ethical, and governance challenges. For cancer data, pilot implementations will be explored through national GDI nodes, the Federated EGA³¹ and collaborations with clinical centres, ensuring that real-world constraints are taken into account.

Finally, WP7 will continue to play an important role in ensuring that requirements from use cases are systematically translated into technical developments and policy frameworks. This includes maintaining alignment across use cases, supporting cross-domain interoperability and contributing to the overall sustainability and scalability of the GDI initiative. In this context, it is anticipated that a significant part of these activities will be further developed and consolidated within a potential GDI extension, where additional time and resources would enable the transition to fully operational, production-ready GDI.

³⁰ <https://erdera.org/>

³¹ <https://ega-archive.org/about/projects-and-funders/federated-ega>

